

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Innovation in services business through diversification of service types to increase customer satisfaction at markas grafis business

A. Nur As Adi, Muhammad Rakib* and Agus Syam

Department of Business and Entrepreneurship, Faculty of Economics and Business, Universitas Negeri Makassar, Indonesia.

World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2025, 25(01), 1402-1414

Publication history: Received on 04 December 2021; revised on 13 January 2025; accepted on 16 January 2025

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2025.25.1.0150>

Abstract

This research aims to develop service innovation in the Markas Grafis business. through diversification of service types to improve customer satisfaction. The subjects of the study consisted of 23 people, namely 20 customers and 3 internal parties of Markas Grafis (Owner, Designer, and Visual Content Manager). This study uses the Substitute, Combine, Adapt, Modify, Put to Another Use, Eliminate, Reverse (SCAMPER) method as the main approach in service development. The research procedure includes customer needs analysis, new service design, diversification implementation, and evaluation of its impact on customer satisfaction. Data were collected through interviews, Voice of Customer (VOC), and observation, which were analyzed thematically to identify changes before and after service development. The results of the study showed that service diversification, such as social media management, vector design, and direct content capture in the field, succeeded in improving service quality and customer satisfaction. This new service is able to meet previously unmet customer needs, provide innovative solutions that are relevant to the demands of the digital era, and open up opportunities to expand market coverage. This study emphasizes the importance of service diversification as a strategic step in responding to the dynamics of customer needs. With continuous innovation, Markas Grafis can continue to compete in the dynamic and competitive graphic design industry.

Keywords: Service diversification; SCAMPER; Graphic Design; Customer satisfaction

1. Introduction

Graphic Design is a creative process that combines art and technology in communicating ideas (Dewojati, 2015). The graphic design service industry continues to experience rapid growth, driven by the increasing needs of businesses and individuals for strong, attractive, and relevant visual identities. Current economic activities are forced to adapt to technological developments. The very rapid development of information and communication technology has occurred in Indonesia today. The position of cash has changed due to technological advances in the payment system, which has given rise to more effective and affordable non-cash payment options (Rakib et al., 2023). This need is not only limited to traditional graphic design, but also extends to more comprehensive solutions, such as social media management, branding strategies, and special designs for specific sectors such as automotive, health, and culinary. This change presents both opportunities and challenges for industry players, including Markas Grafis, to remain relevant, competitive, and able to meet increasingly complex customer needs. Improving the quality of human resources needs to be handled by the government. Quality human resources are assets in the field of labor and experts who can transform Indonesia into a competitive country compared to other countries, especially in the current era (Rakib, 2016).

Companies with competitive advantages can maintain their position because they have the ability to attract consumers. Although SMEs face many obstacles such as lack of innovation resources, methodologies, and management skills, it is clear that innovation remains popular among SMEs worldwide. Business Innovation and Competitive Advantage

* Corresponding author: Muhammad Rakib.

Innovation is a key factor in several aspects of business competition. Innovation allows companies to bring new or improved products to the market before their competitors, thereby increasing their market share (Rakib, 2023).

The Influence of Creative Industries on the Local Economy The economic development of a region is an important pillar for the implementation of the development process in all fields (Rakib et al., 2018). Markas Grafis as one of the players in the graphic design industry faces a big challenge to continue to innovate in creating services that are not only visually appealing but also have strategic value for customers. With increasing customer expectations and tight competition, Markas Grafis needs to develop a new approach that is able to answer market needs while strengthening customer loyalty.

This study aims to answer these needs by applying the SCAMPER method as a service innovation framework. The SCAMPER method consisting of seven dimensions (Substitute, Combine, Adapt, Modify, Put to Another Use, Eliminate, and Reverse) was chosen because of its ability to encourage creative thinking and innovative solutions. By using this method, the study focuses on service diversification that includes social media management, vector design, to direct content capture in the field.

The results of the application of this method are expected to not only help Markas Grafis provide more varied and relevant services, but also improve the quality of teamwork, response to customer needs, and operational effectiveness. This research is expected to provide practical contributions to Markas Grafis' efforts in improving service quality and customer satisfaction, as well as being a reference for other graphic design industry players in facing similar challenges in the digital era.

2. Literature review

2.1. Graphic design

The opinion of (Musmuliadi & Purmadi, 2019) states that graphic design is a form of visual communication using text or images to convey information or messages as effectively as possible so that graphic design art can include cognitive abilities and visual skills including typography, image processing and page layout because in graphic design, text is also considered an image because it is the result of abstraction of symbols that can be sounded, like other types of design graphic design can refer to the manufacturing process, the method of designing a product produced or the design discipline used.

In graphic design, there are several important principles that must be considered to produce effective work. Simplicity is the main key so that the message conveyed can be easily understood by the reader. In addition, visual balance is also very important, where design elements must face each other and create a balanced impression. The principle of unity is also no less important, because a design must have cohesion, consistency, and integrity that make the overall composition feel harmonious. Emphasis is needed to draw the reader's attention to the part of the design that you want to emphasize, so that the main message can be conveyed clearly. Finally, rhythm in graphic design includes the interval of space or distance between objects, which serves to create a pleasing visual rhythm and guide the reader in understanding the design as a whole.

2.2. Service Diversification Strategy

Diversification is an effort to synergize between the main business and the new business from diversification. through business segments (Sumail, 2015). Diversification strategy is a strategy with the most complex implications because for companies that diversify it will be a new experience, both in terms of its market and its products. (Lucius Hermawan, 2015), Every diversification decision will experience high business risk. The company must conduct research first. By looking at the distribution aspect whether it has been running well or not because distribution plays an important role in diversification. Another important factor is that every diversification product is indeed in demand by consumers where the company must pay attention to its products in terms of quality. Before the diversification product enters the market, a market test must be carried out first, so that it is understood whether the product is well received or not.

In a business context, diversification includes not only product development, but also services. Companies can expand or diversify their services to achieve growth, take advantage of new opportunities, and reduce risk. Service diversification can involve adding new services that did not previously exist, or developing existing services to be more relevant to customer needs. In this way, companies can reach more customers, create more diverse revenue streams, and improve their competitive position in the market. However, companies must ensure that such diversification is aligned with their capabilities and market needs so as not to add operational complexity.

2.3. Customer satisfaction

Customer satisfaction is a part related to the creation of customer value. Because the creation of customer satisfaction means providing benefits to the company, namely, among others, the relationship between the company and its customers becomes harmonious, provides a good foundation or creates customer satisfaction and forms a word of mouth recommendation that is beneficial for the company, so that there is interest from customers to buy or use the company's services (Sambodo Rio Sasongko, 2021). This is because this step can provide feedback and input for the purposes of developing and implementing strategies to increase customer satisfaction. Customer satisfaction with products and services is the main factor in deciding to buy a product (Sanusi, Widodo, et al., 2023). However, satisfaction in buying a product cannot be separated from consumer behavior which is influenced by lifestyle (Sanusi, Tunjanan, et al., 2023). Customer satisfaction can be measured through four main methods, namely the first is the complaint and suggestion system.

3. Research methods

This study uses a qualitative-based development model with the SCAMPER approach as the main framework for service innovation at Markas Grafis. The SCAMPER model was chosen because of its systematic and flexible nature in identifying innovation opportunities and improving service quality. This method allows the implementation of service changes based on seven dimensions designed to answer customer needs and expand market reach through diversification of service types.

The research procedure begins with customer needs analysis through interviews, observations, and VOC. The next stage is the design of new services, which includes the incorporation of innovative ideas by utilizing the SCAMPER framework. After design, implementation is carried out by introducing service diversification to customers. The final step is evaluation, where the effectiveness of new services is assessed based on customer feedback and analysis of changes in customer satisfaction before and after development.

The focus of this study is to evaluate the level of customer satisfaction with the diversification of services implemented at Markas Grafis, including new services such as Social Media Agency, vector design, and field content management. The study also aims to understand how the SCAMPER approach can improve service quality, meet customer needs, and strengthen their loyalty. The main indicators analyzed include customer experience, expectations, and their needs before and after service development.

The research subjects consisted of 23 respondents, including 20 Markas Grafis customers as a representation of service users and 3 internal parties of Markas Grafis, namely the owner, visual content manager, and graphic designer. Respondents were selected purposively to obtain a comprehensive perspective on service quality, both from the customer and business actors' perspectives. The research data sources consisted of primary and secondary data. Primary data was obtained through interviews, VOCs filled in by customers, and direct observation during the research process. Meanwhile, secondary data came from Markas Grafis internal documents, academic journals, and related literature, which provided additional context to support thematic analysis.

Data collection techniques used include interviews with internal parties of Markas Grafis, VOC from customers, and direct observation during the implementation of service diversification. Interviews were conducted to obtain information about customer experiences, needs, and expectations. VOC was used to collect free responses from customers regarding their satisfaction with the service before and after development. Observations were used to record changes in work processes and interactions during service development.

Data analysis was conducted using a thematic approach to identify patterns, themes, and relationships in the data obtained. Data from interviews and VOCs were analyzed through a coding process, where each response was categorized based on key themes such as service quality, responsiveness to customer needs, and customer satisfaction. The results of the thematic analysis provide insight into changes that occurred before and after service development, thus providing a comprehensive picture of the effectiveness of the SCAMPER approach in improving service quality and customer satisfaction.

4. Results

Diversifying services through the SCAMPER method has proven to be a very effective strategy in increasing competitiveness and customer satisfaction. Through the application of the seven dimensions of SCAMPER, Markas Grafis has succeeded in adding various new services, such as social media management, vector design, and direct content capture in the field. This addition not only answers previously unmet customer needs, but also opens up new market opportunities by reaching a wider customer segment, including business people from various sectors such as automotive, health, and culinary. With this diversification, Markas Grafis is able to strengthen its business position amidst increasingly tight competition in the graphic design industry.

Figure 1 Results of service development using the SCAMPER method

4.1. Substitute

This stage is carried out by replacing the old service in the form of graphic design with a new service, namely Graphic Design & Social Media Agency. This change was made to respond to increasingly complex customer needs, especially in the field of social media management. With this new service, it is hoped that the market reach can be wider and customer needs for integrated social media management can be met.

Table 1 Replaced services

Category	Before (Replace)	After (Replace)
Type of Service	Graphic design	Graphic Design and Social Media Agency
Target Market	Students and MSMEs	Students, SMEs, Organizations and Companies
Range	Friends of Friends	National
Value-added	Visual Design	Digital and Visual Strategy

4.2. Combine

This stage is done by combining Social Media Agency services and logo design into one service package. The purpose of this merger is to provide a more integrated solution for customers. With this service, graphic headquarters customers not only get a logo design that reflects their brand identity, but also a social media management strategy that supports promotions and increases overall brand appeal.

Figure 2 Integration of Logo Design and Social Media Agency

4.3. Adapt

Adjustments are made using the Meta Suite Manager technology feature to simplify content management, such as post scheduling and customer interaction. This technology helps teams manage multiple social media accounts in one platform.

4.3.1. Content Scheduling

Figure 3 Content Upload Process Using Meta Suite Manager

4.3.2. Scheduled Content

Figure 4 Content Scheduling Process in Meta Suite Manager

4.3.3. Content Results Analysis

Figure 5 Analysis of uploaded content in Meta Suite Manager

4.4. Modify

Modifications are made by adding various types of new graphic design services. This addition aims to provide more diverse choices to customers according to their visual needs.

Table 2 List of Services after Diversification

Category	Service Before	Additional Services
Promotional Print Design (Print Media)	Poster Design	Flyer Design
	Pamphlet Design	Packaging Label Design
	Banner/X-Banner Design	Calendar Design
	Brochure Design	Billboard Design
	Certificate Design	
Branding and Visual Identity Design	Logo Design	Packaging Design
	Business Card Design	Product Mock-up Design
	Packaging Label Design	
Digital Design and social media	Instagram Feed Design	Social Media Ads Design
		Wallpaper Design
		Presentation Design (PPT)
Book Design and Publication		Book or E-book Design
		Book/Album Cover Design
		Catalog Design
		Infographic Design
Merchandise Design and Physical Products	T-Shirt Design	Sticker Design
	Tote bag Design	Invitation Design

Specialization Design		Backdrop/Stage Design
		Menu Design
Illustration and Graphic Design		Vector Design
		Bitmap Vectorization Design

4.5. Put to another use

Design services are adapted for specific sectors such as automotive, health, and culinary, with different focuses according to the needs of each sector. This can be seen in the following table:

Table 3 Special Sector Designs

Sector	Design Focus	Implementation Example
Automotive	Superiority	The advantages of using vehicle cleaning products
Health	Health Education and Promotion	Education on the importance of paying attention to symbols on recycled products
Culinary	Visual Appeal of Food	More prominent food portraits

The following are the design results after developing SCAMPER in 3 types of business sectors

Vehicle Cleaning Products	Health Education	Culinary
The design emphasizes the product's superiority	Educational design on the importance of paying attention to recycling symbols	The design emphasizes food products more

Figure 6 Design results in special sectors

4.6. Eliminate

This stage aims to eliminate irrelevant or potentially controversial elements, thus creating more professional and acceptable results for various groups. An example is avoiding the use of content that is not in accordance with the field of graphic design, such as elements that do not support the aesthetics or message of the design, or content that contains sensitive issues such as SARA (Ethnicity, Religion, Race, and Intergroup). In addition, elements that do not provide added value or direct benefits to customers are also removed. This is done to ensure more focused, relevant, and high-quality services, so as to increase the level of customer satisfaction and trust in the services provided.

Figure 7 Before and After Content Elimination

4.7. Reverse

The communication approach has changed from previously only using chat to being more flexible with phone options. This aims to provide convenience and increase the efficiency of communication with customers.

Table 4 Reversal of Communication Method

Communication Methods	Before	After	Impact
Chat	Limited	Still in Use	Stay flexible for short messages
Telephone	Not available	Available	Improve clarity and time efficiency

The following are the results of the research data analysis conducted using the thematic method, which involved various important parties in the evaluation process, namely Customers, Owners, Designers, and Visual Content Managers, both before service development and after comprehensive and targeted service development was carried out at Markas Grafis.

This analysis was structured by identifying the main themes, which were then grouped into sub-themes to provide more specific details. Data were obtained from various sources, such as interviews and observations, which were then compared between pre-development and post-development to find changes or impacts that occurred. All data were analyzed and categorized into thematic codes, which helped identify relevant patterns or trends in this study.

The results of the thematic analysis revealed that Markas Grafis customer satisfaction is influenced by several important factors, such as creativity and design quality, ability to meet customer expectations, timeliness of work, clarity of communication, balance between price and results, relevance of design to trends, and diversity of services available. Before the development was carried out, many customers expressed dissatisfaction regarding the design results that were less innovative, slow work duration, ineffective communication, and inconsistencies between costs incurred and results received.

Table 5 Results of Thematic Method Analysis

Theme	Sub-themes	Data source	Pre-Development (Findings)	Post-Development (Findings)	Code/Category
Quality of Graphic Design Services	Design Quality	Interview	There needs to be improvements in graphic design services, such as more variety in designs to meet client needs.	After development, graphic design services are more diverse, and the design results produced are also more creative and not monotonous.	Service Variety, Design Creativity
Conformity to Expectations	Design Expectations	Voice of Costumer (VOC)	The design received did not match expectations, many customers felt dissatisfied with the design results.	After development, more designs meet customer expectations, with more attractive design innovations and variations.	Conformity to Expectations, Design Innovation
Project Completion Time	Punctuality	Interview	Project completion times often do not match what was promised, and sometimes affect quality.	The project was completed on time after improvements in time management and more efficient task allocation.	Time Management, Efficiency
Communication Process	Effective Communication	Voice of Costumer (VOC)	Sometimes there are difficulties in communication that affect the understanding of the desired design.	The communication process has been running more smoothly since the development, and there is more frequent confirmation about the design process.	Communication Effectiveness, Clarity
Service Price	Price Match	Voice of Costumer (VOC)	The price is too high compared to the results obtained.	More affordable price with better quality after development, according to customer expectations.	Price Match, Customer Satisfaction
Special Needs	Design Needs	Interview	Some customers want designs for social media and other promotional materials that are more in line with current trends.	After development, social media designs are more in line with the needs and trends in the market.	Social Media Design, Design Trends
Suggestions for Service Development	Service Development	Voice of Costumer (VOC)	Providing more varied services and designs for more diverse social media platforms.	Service development is good, but some customers still want more varied designs and more options for social media platforms.	Service Development, Social Media Design

After the development of services based on the SCAMPER method, real improvements were found in various aspects. Customers felt an increase in design creativity, timeliness in workmanship, and better communication, so that their needs could be understood and accommodated more optimally. Adjusting prices to the quality of results is also an important point appreciated by customers, because it provides more value according to their expectations.

Overall, the development of this service shows success in increasing customer satisfaction, although there is potential to continue to improve and add variety to the service to be more diverse and in accordance with market demands. This finding emphasizes the need for consistent innovation and continuous evaluation to maintain the competitiveness and relevance of services in the future.

5. Discussion

The results of this study indicate that the application of the SCAMPER method in the development of graphic design services at Markas Grafis has a positive impact on improving service quality and customer satisfaction. Based on thematic analysis conducted on Voice of Customer (VOC) data and interviews, real changes were found before and after service development. Before the implementation of SCAMPER, Markas Grafis services were considered less varied and less responsive to customer needs, so customers felt that their needs were not fully met. However, after the development, new services such as social media management, vector design, and direct content capture in the field proved successful in meeting previously neglected customer needs.

This finding is in line with the theory (Kotler, 2016) which emphasizes that experience, customer expectations, and needs are the three main indicators in measuring customer satisfaction. This study shows that all three indicators increased overall after service development. From customer experience, interview results revealed that the communication process and speed of project completion improved. In terms of expectations, customers stated that the new service was in line with their expectations, while customer needs were met through diversification of service types that included various graphic design needs and digital content management.

In addition, the results of this study also support the findings of (Lindung Bulan, 2012), which states that product or service diversification has a positive impact on customer satisfaction. In previous studies, diversification provides more choices to consumers, which creates its own satisfaction. Similar things were also found at Markas Grafis, where the addition of new services increased the flexibility of choice for customers, thereby improving their overall experience. The implementation of the SCAMPER method also succeeded in improving the customer feedback management system. Before development, customer input was often not followed up properly, which created a gap in communication. However, after development, the internal team became more responsive by holding regular evaluation sessions to follow up on customer suggestions. This is consistent with the opinion of (Azzahrah, 2023), which highlights that SCAMPER is an effective approach in creating sustainable innovation that responds to customer needs more comprehensively.

Not only does it improve the quality of service, development through the SCAMPER method also has a positive impact on the efficiency of internal work processes at Markas Grafis. Before the development, technological limitations caused the work process to be slow and less structured. However, the implementation of technology such as Meta Suite Manager allows the team to manage content scheduling automatically, saving time and increasing productivity. This more efficient work process also allows the team to focus more on design innovations that are relevant to customer needs.

The results of the study also showed an increase in customer loyalty after the development. Many customers who previously only used Markas Grafis services for certain needs are now regular customers and even recommend the service to others. This is supported by the theory (Sambodo Rio Sasongko, 2021) which states that customer satisfaction can create a harmonious relationship between the company and customers and encourage loyalty through word of mouth recommendations. Thus, the results of this study provide evidence that the implementation of the SCAMPER method not only improves service quality and customer satisfaction but also improves Markas Grafis' internal system. Service diversification has proven to be a strategic step in responding to customer needs in the digital era, creating loyalty, and maintaining competitiveness in the dynamic graphic design industry.

6. Conclusion

This study concludes that the application of the SCAMPER method in service development at Markas Grafis has succeeded in improving service quality and customer satisfaction. Through this approach, new services that are more

relevant to customer needs, such as creative design, faster work, and more effective communication, have been successfully implemented. This innovation is able to answer customer needs that were previously less accommodated, while providing added value in the form of price compliance with quality and design that follows current trends. This improvement also shows that service innovation through SCAMPER is able to overcome the main challenges in customer satisfaction, such as clarity of communication, timeliness, and design results that meet expectations. This approach opens up new opportunities for Markas Grafis to reach a wider market segment and strengthen relationships with customers. Thus, this study confirms that planned and continuously developing service innovation is very important to maintain competitiveness and business growth in the dynamic graphic design industry.

Markas Grafis is expected to continue to maintain and improve its service innovation by paying more attention to customer input. Emphasis on the use of the latest technology, such as automation in social media management and customer data analysis, will help improve efficiency and service quality. In addition, expanding the reach of services to other relevant industry segments can also be an effective strategy to increase market share and maintain competitiveness. For further research, this study is still limited to service development and customer satisfaction measurement. Therefore, further research is recommended to explore other aspects such as digital marketing, the effectiveness of promotional strategies, and cost analysis related to the impact of service diversification. With this approach, it is hoped that future research results can provide more comprehensive insights into the sustainability and potential for business growth in the context of service diversification. For other industry players, the SCAMPER method applied in this study can be used as a relevant service innovation model, especially for businesses in the creative industry sector. By adopting this approach, companies can design services that are more adaptive to customer needs and become more competitive in an increasingly developing market.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

References

- [1] Azzahrah, A. A. (2023). Product Diversification to Increase Consumer Satisfaction: A Development Research Study. *International Journal of Current Science Research and Review*, 06(11), 7291–7296. <https://doi.org/10.47191/ijcsrr/v6-i11-33>
- [2] Dewojati, R. K. W. (2015). Desain Grafis Sebagai Media Ungkap Periklanan. *Imaji*, 7(2). <https://doi.org/10.21831/imaji.v7i2.6633>
- [3] Kotler, P. and K. L. K. (2016). *Marketing Management*, 15 th ed, Pearson Education Limited, New York. 4(August), 30–59.
- [4] Lindung Bulan, T. P. (2012). Pengaruh Diversifikasi Produk dan Harga terhadap Kepuasan Konsumen pada Juragan Jasmine Langsa. *Jurnal Manajemen Dan Keuangan*, 6(1), 679–687.
- [5] Lucius Hermawan. (2015). Dilema Diversifikasi Produk: Meningkatkan Pendapatan Atau Menimbulkan Kanibalisme Produk? *Jurnal Studi Manajemen*, 9(2), 142–153.
- [6] Musmuliadi, M., & Purmadi, A. (2019). Pengaruh Media Desain Grafis Berbasis Adobe Photoshop Terhadap Kreativitas Belajar Siswa. *Jurnal Teknologi Pendidikan : Jurnal Penelitian Dan Pengembangan Pembelajaran*, 3(1), 20. <https://doi.org/10.33394/jtp.v3i1.1223>
- [7] Rakib, M. (2016). Entrepreneurship Education Development In Dealing Asean Economic Community. *Proceedings of Icmstea*, October, 280–285.
- [8] Rakib, M. (2023). Impact of Digital Literacy, Business Innovation, Competitive Advantage on the Existence of SMEs A quantitative study in Indonesia. *Quality - Access to Success*, 25(198), 277-283. <https://doi.org/10.47750/QAS/25.198.30>
- [9] Rakib, M., Arafah, S., & Sanusi, D. A. (2023). Teknologi Finansial, E-Commerce, Perkembangan Alternatif Pembayaran dan Kinerja Bisnis Toko Online: Suatu Kajian pada Mahasiswa Ekonomi dan Bisnis. *Jurnal Pendidikan Akuntansi (JPak)*, 11(1), 87–95. <https://doi.org/10.26740/jpak.v11n1.p87-95>

- [10] Rakib, M., Yunus, M., & Amin, N. (2018). Creative Industry Development Based on Entrepreneurship Training in Developing Local Economy in Parepare City. *OIKOS Jurnal Kajian Pendidikan Ekonomi dan Ilmu Ekonomi*. 2 (1), 32-46. <https://doi.org/10.23969/oikos.v2i1.923>
- [11] Sambodo Rio Sasongko. (2021). Faktor-Faktor Kepuasan Pelanggan Dan Loyalitas Pelanggan (Literature Review Manajemen Pemasaran). *Jurnal Ilmu Manajemen Terapan*, 3(1), 104–114. <https://doi.org/10.31933/jimt.v3i1.707>
- [12] Sanusi, D. A., Tunjangan, L., & Sajow, D. (2023). Do the Lifestyle and Socio-Economic Status of Students ' Parents Affect Students ' Consumption Behavior ? An empirical study on Satya Wiyata Mandala University Students. 1(3), 156–161.
- [13] Sanusi, D. A., Widodo, A., & Tunjangan, L. (2023). Media Literacy, Consumer Trust, Product Prices, Distribution, and Purchasing Decisions in Online Business: A Study of Students at Satya Wiyata Mandala University. *Indonesian Journal of Business and Entrepreneurship Research*, 1(1), 52–61. <https://journal.unm.ac.id/index.php/IJOB/article/view/119%0Ahttps://journal.unm.ac.id/index.php/IJOB/ER/article/download/119/110>
- [14] Sumail, M. & L. O. (2015). Strategi Diversifikasi Dan Komitmen Tatakelola Pada Perbankan Syariah Di Kota Makassar. *XIX(03)*, 387–397.